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ETHICS IN GEORGIAN PUBLIC SERVICE: EVOLUTION AND CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES

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Abstract

This study delves into the level of consumer rights awareness among Tbilisi school students. By analyzing factors influencing this awareness, the research identifies a significant knowledge gap, particularly in areas like product composition, complaint filing, and online shopping security. To address this, the study recommends integrating consumer education into the school curriculum, emphasizing interactive learning methods and real-world applications. Additionally, collaborations with consumer protection organizations and universities can enhance the effectiveness of these initiatives. By empowering young people with consumer rights knowledge, we can foster a more informed and responsible consumer society in Georgia.

Keywords: Consumer rights, consumer education, youth awareness, consumer protection, economic literacy, social responsibility.

Introduction

Ethics, a cornerstone of philosophical inquiry, examines the principles of human morality. Originating from the ancient Greek term "ethos," which means habit or custom, ethics was first formally introduced by Aristotle. However, its roots extend further back to the philosophical musings of Socrates and Plato. These early philosophers sought to intertwine moral understanding with philosophical systems, establishing morality as a framework of norms and principles governing human behavior.

The German philosopher Immanuel Kant elevated ethics above all sciences, asserting that while other sciences provide the conditions for human life, ethics defines its purpose and meaning. Modern definitions of ethics highlight its role as a systematic endeavor to derive guiding principles from individual and societal moral experiences, emphasizing the necessity of distinguishing right from wrong.

In the context of public service, particularly in Georgia, ethics plays a critical role in shaping the behavior and actions of civil servants. The journey of ethical development in Georgia's public service has been marked by significant legislative milestones. Starting with the 1997 Law "On Civil Service," which laid down general conduct guidelines for civil servants, to more recent reforms such as the 2015 Law "On Public Service" and the 2017 Government Decree on ethics, these frameworks aim to instill integrity, transparency, and accountability within the public sector.

This article delves into the evolution and current trends of ethics in Georgia, exploring the legislative measures, the practical implications for civil servants, and the overarching importance of ethical principles in fostering a trustworthy and effective public service. Through a detailed examination, we aim to shed light on the continuous process of ethical standard formation and the critical role it plays in combating misconduct

and corruption, ultimately ensuring the implementation of good faith and public trust in state institutions.

1. The Essence of Ethics and Its Development Trends in Georgia

Ethics is seen as a component of philosophy that studies human morality. The term "ethics" is of ancient Greek origin, derived from the word "ethos," which means habit or custom. The term "ethics" was first introduced by the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle (382-322 BC). However, issues of ethics were addressed much earlier by Socrates (470-399 BC) and Plato (427-347 BC). The interest of ancient Greek philosophers in ethical issues is not surprising, as ethics was considered a philosophical discipline. The study of morality without philosophical understanding was deemed unthinkable;¹ thus, their philosophical systems were created to build ethical doctrines.² Morality was viewed as a set of norms and principles regulating people's lives.

The great German philosopher Kant (1724-1804) believed that ethics is superior to all other sciences because while other sciences create the conditions for human life, ethics explores what human life means and what it ought to be. Ethics studies the goal, while other sciences study the means of achieving this goal.³

There is no single, specific definition of ethics. According to one definition, ethics is seen as a systematic attempt to thoroughly use individual and public moral experiences to define the guiding rules of human behavior. Ethics is related to the definition of right and wrong; it is the search for moral standards. The issue of separating ethics and morality is important. Focusing on ethics emphasizes the active involvement of the individual in the search for a morally correct position. Ethics demands action, thinking, analysis, and the identification of justified behavior. However, solving various ethical dilemmas arising from the activities of a

¹ Badzagua, M., *Fundamentals of Professional Ethics*, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 10.

² Bandzeladze, G., *Ethics*, Tbilisi, 1966, p. 73.

³ *Ibid.*, p. 12.

public institution may rarely present clearly right or wrong actions.⁴

Ethics defines certain obligations aimed at creating a better environment. It is one of the important values for people of different professions, be it politics, science, education, or others.⁵

The purpose of ethical conduct is to prevent and suppress misconduct within the state and society, eliminate corruption, and ensure the implementation of the principle of good faith.⁶ The formation of ethical standards is an ongoing process that requires regular consideration and refinement to adapt to changing circumstances and emerging ethical challenges.

The general rules of conduct for civil servants were defined in the 1997 edition of the Law of Georgia "On Civil Service." This law aimed to establish general principles regulating the behavior of civil servants in the performance of their official duties. According to the 1997 edition, a separate chapter was dedicated to the general rules of conduct for civil servants. This chapter included guidelines for issuing and using public information, managing conflicts of interest, and preventing corruption.

Despite these measures, the necessity for a unified administrative mechanism to protect ethical norms was identified as a key need in Resolution №627 of the Government of Georgia, which approved the concept of civil service reform and related measures. As a result of this reform, the Parliament of Georgia adopted a new Law "On Public Service" in October 2015. Additionally, amendments were made to the Law "On Conflict of Interest and Corruption in Public Institutions."⁷ Finally, on April 20, 2017, the Government of Georgia issued Decree N200 on the "Determination of General Rules of Ethics."

The norms defined in these legislative acts (along with any other specific norms) regulate the standard of behavior for civil servants.

2. Legal Regulation of the Standard of Conduct for Civil Servants

Activity in public service in Georgia encompasses all activities carried out by civil servants, except⁸ for those activities defined as exceptions by the Law of Georgia "On Public Service." This includes activities in municipal institutions and legal entities under public law, excluding cultural, educational, scientific, research, sports, and religious organizations, as well as membership-based legal entities defined by the law. Public service is considered within various offices, including the administration of the President of Georgia, the Office of the Prime Minister and the Government of Georgia, the Office of the National Bank of Georgia, the Office of the State Audit Office, the Office of the High Council of Justice of Georgia, the Office of the

Public Defender of Georgia, the Office of the Business Ombudsman of Georgia, and the administration of the state representative.

Public service is carried out by civil servants, who can be categorized into three types: professional civil servants, persons employed under an administrative contract, and persons employed under a labor contract.⁹ Among these, professional civil servants hold the leading position within the civil service system due to their functional roles and workloads, which are considered the primary managerial functions.¹⁰

The general rules of ethics and conduct in public service are regulated by several legislative acts, including the Law of Georgia "On Public Service," the Law of Georgia "On Combating Corruption," and the Government of Georgia's decree "On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in Public Institutions" (April 20, 2017, N200). Additionally, if specific rules of ethics exist for certain public servants, these special rules may apply alongside the general rules established by the mentioned legislative regulations.

Article 77 of the Law of Georgia "On Public Service" outlines additional rights and obligations for officials, specifically stating that compliance with the general rules of ethics and conduct is mandated by the Law of Georgia "On Combating Corruption." This law defines who qualifies as a civil servant for its purposes, detailing that it includes professional civil servants, individuals employed under administrative contracts in the civil service, and officials listed in the first paragraph of Article 2. It clarifies that persons employed under labor contracts are not considered public servants, except where exceptions are established by Georgian legislative acts. This reservation indicates that a person employed under a labor contract in the civil service, who is otherwise considered a public servant, must adhere to certain ethical standards.

Additionally, the Government of Georgia's decree "On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in Public Institutions" (April 20, 2017, No. 200) addresses the issue of incompatibility of interests and the distribution of gift regulatory norms for civil servants employed under labor contracts. This decree includes an exceptional provision stipulating that the norms regulating the incompatibility of interests and the acceptance of gifts apply to these individuals. However, this should not be interpreted as exempting them from the obligation to prioritize public interest. All legal status subjects employed in public service must protect and prioritize public interests. In cases where public and private interests conflict, the fact that the regulation on the incompatibility of interests does not apply

⁴ Denhart, R., Denhart, J., Public Management, Ilia State University, 2012, p. 200.

⁵ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Tskhvalashvili, T. eds.), Ethics and General Rules of Conduct in the Civil Service, Tbilisi, 2015, p. 7.

⁶ Author Collective, Management and Leadership in Public Service, Civil Service Bureau, 2020, p. 71.

⁷ Law of Georgia on the "Fight Against Corruption".

⁸ Persons defined in the first paragraph of Article 4 of the Law of Georgia "On Public Service".

⁹ Subparagraph "c" of Article 3 of the Law of Georgia "On Public Service".

¹⁰ Dvalishvili, I., Turava, K., Kardava, E., Makalatia, M., Dvalishvili, N., Tsulaia, A., Pirtskhalaishvili, Z., Kardava, E. (Eds.), Comments on the Law of Georgia on Civil Service, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 20.

to someone employed under a labor contract cannot justify making decisions based on private interests.¹¹

The mentioned decree also sets exceptional conditions for employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Georgia, establishing that the rules of ethics and conduct apply to them unless otherwise specified by special legislation.¹² Furthermore, special norms may regulate various issues differently in other cases. For example, Article 13 (11) of the Law of Georgia "On Combating Corruption" states that the article on incompatibility of interests applies to members of the Parliament of Georgia unless otherwise prescribed by the rules of procedure of the Parliament of Georgia.¹³ The rules of procedure stipulate that the ethical standards of behavior for members of Parliament are determined by their code of ethics, which is approved by the Parliament.

Accordingly, this confirms that the general rules of ethics and conduct apply to civil servants alongside any special rules of ethics and/or conduct established for them, if such rules exist.

3. The Importance of Protecting the Ethical Principles of a Civil Servant

Adherence to ethical principles in any profession is crucial for establishing an effective standard of conduct that promotes more effective, accountable, and transparent governance. This benefits both the relationship with the state and public relations/accountability. Acting in compliance with ethical principles in public service is vital for the effective functioning of institutions, which, in turn, ensures the proper protection of public interests.

Each principle of activity in the civil service, as defined within the legislative framework of Georgia, plays a significant role in ensuring the implementation of effective managerial activities. Upon entering the civil service, a civil servant undertakes to act in accordance with the principles of civil service, ethics, and rules of conduct. The Law of Georgia "On Public Service" dedicates a separate chapter to the principles of public service and defines the following principles: legality, loyalty, equality before the law, economy and efficiency, merit-based public service, impartiality, equal access to public service, accountability, political neutrality, and social and legal protection of civil servants. At the same time, the Law of Georgia "On Combating Corruption" and the Government of Georgia's decree "On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct" (2017, No. 200) combine the guiding principles and values of the civil service. These legislative regulations clarify the principles of activity in the

public service, which should guide individuals employed in the public service.

Acting on the principle of loyalty imposes an obligation on a public servant to carry out official activities in good faith. This should be expressed in decisions made or accepted within the framework of the functions and duties assigned to them, ensuring that any actions comply with the law and serve the interests of the people and the state.¹⁴ Public servants should prioritize the needs of society over personal benefit or their own interests. They should be responsible for their actions and decisions, facilitating the process of gaining and maintaining public trust in public institutions.

Commitment to the state ensures transparent, non-discriminatory, and neutral decisions. Accordingly, when a public servant makes decisions based on objective circumstances, acts impartially, understands the factors causing any kind of conflict of interest, and makes discrimination-free decisions, they uphold their obligations to the people and the state and act in accordance with the principle of loyalty.¹⁵

An important principle of activity in the public service is the principle of legality, which, along with other principles, is fundamental. Any action of a civil servant should be based on the principles of the rule of law and legal reservation.¹⁶

Acting in accordance with the principle of neutrality obliges a public servant to be free and neutral when making decisions, separating state interests from those of any personal political party or religious association to which they may belong. The goal of political neutrality is to ensure that civil service remains separate from political interests, creating a politically neutral civil service. While a civil servant has the right to support any political ideology, this support should not influence their official decisions.¹⁷

Similarly, acting in accordance with the principle of religious neutrality requires public servants to remain free and neutral when making decisions, ensuring state interests are separate from those of any personal religious community or association to which they may belong. Although the Constitution of Georgia does not explicitly mention norms of religious neutrality, it establishes the freedom of faith, religion, and conscience for every person. Additionally, the constitutional principle of equality before the law includes religious communities, obliging the state to ensure equal benefits as guaranteed by law, which implies the religious neutrality of the state.¹⁸

The freedom of expression of public servants is a significant issue concerning ethics and standards of conduct. A civil servant, as a citizen, does not lose their freedom of expression when they enter public service;

¹¹ Law of Georgia on the "Fight Against Corruption", Art. 21.

¹² Government of Georgia, On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Decree of April 20, 2017, No. 200, Article 2, Paragraph 3.

¹³ Rules of Procedure of the Parliament of Georgia, Article 227, Paragraph 1.

¹⁴ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Kardava, E. ed.), On Approval of the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Comments on the Decree of the Government of Georgia, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 24.

¹⁵ Ibid., pp. 27-28.

¹⁶ Law of Georgia on "Public Service", Art. 7.

¹⁷ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Kardava, E. ed.), On Approval of the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Comments on the Decree of the Government of Georgia, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 33.

¹⁸ Government of Georgia, On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Decree of April 20, 2017, No. 200, Art. 7.

however, there are certain restrictions under the legislation. For instance, a public servant, other than one in a leadership position, may publicly express their views on the policies of the public institution where they work, provided these opinions do not concern issues directly within their official authority or knowledge gained through their official role. In such cases, the public servant must indicate that their views do not represent the position of the public institution.¹⁹

"Incompatibility of interests in a public institution" refers to the conflict between a public servant's personal or property interests and the interests of the public institution.²⁰ A "conflict of interest" is defined as a situation where a civil servant's private interests may unduly influence the performance of their public duties.²¹

There are three types of incompatibility of interests: real, visible, and potential.

Real Incompatibility of Interests: This occurs when a civil servant's private interests directly conflict with their official duties. For example, a civil servant receiving income from an organization they oversee creates a real conflict of interest.

Visible Conflict of Interest: This occurs when a civil servant formally declares a conflict of interest. For instance, if a civil servant officially declares ownership of shares in a business and, based on a trust agreement, transfers the management of these shares to another person for the duration of their service, this represents a visible conflict of interest.

Potential Conflict of Interest: This occurs when a conflict of interest might arise if circumstances change.²² For example, a civil servant who owns shares in a company that could potentially become a service provider for the public institution where they work in a decision-making capacity faces a potential conflict of interest. Sources of potential conflicts may include additional activities that, while compatible, might still influence the civil servant's main duties improperly.

Article 9 (2) of the resolution of the Government of Georgia "On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution" states that a public servant should avoid circumstances that may be perceived as direct or indirect influence of private interest on their official activities. This provision is preventive, aiming to avoid the occurrence of potential incompatibility of interests. It obliges public servants to steer clear of any circumstances that might be perceived as influencing their official activities.

Direct Influence: This might occur when a public servant is part of a tender commission responsible for selecting a winning company. Due to their position, they can directly influence the commission's decision.

Indirect Influence: This might occur when a public servant's private interests, even if not directly involved, can still influence the final decision. For instance, a public servant's relationship with a company participating in a tender can create an indirect influence on the outcome, especially if the public servant has a vested interest in the company.²³

The following activities are considered compatible with the position occupied by a public servant: scientific activities, pedagogical activities, creative activities, and sports activities. Each compatible activity has a specific definition. For example, scientific activity includes the creation and publication of scientific works or articles, participation in various scientific conferences and seminars, as well as the implementation of scientific research activities. Pedagogical activity includes conducting lectures, seminars, and trainings, as well as sharing and transferring professional knowledge and experience in other forms. Creative activity is considered the creation, restoration, and/or interpretation of cultural values, both in material and intangible forms.

The definition of sports activities is particularly interesting. Although its exact definition is not clear, its inclusion in the list of compatible activities may cause differences of opinion.²⁴ The definition of sports activities is not found in the Law of Georgia "On Sports," but the state policy document on sports (2014-2020) specifies that sports include all forms of physical activity, whether irregular or organized, aimed at improving physical and mental abilities, developing public relations, and achieving results in competitions of all levels.²⁵ This general definition raises questions about what is meant by all forms of physical activity and whether the activities of sports referees, coaches, athletes, or professional athletes are covered. For example, whether sports activities include those for whom sport is the main source of income.

It would be beneficial if legislative regulation could clearly define what sports activities mean and what types of sports activities can be considered compatible, to avoid mixed practices in the public service. It is also noteworthy that certain activities, such as those in the cultural sphere, are not listed among compatible activities. The potential conflicts of interest arising from activities in the cultural sphere need to be revised and newly defined by legislation.²⁶

It is important to outline specific criteria for evaluating compatible activities, which would give employers the opportunity to discuss, evaluate, and resolve issues of conflict of interest in each specific case. However, there should not be any gaps in such regulations, and the issue of whether or not to carry out a particular

¹⁹ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Kardava, E. ed.), On Approval of the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Comments on the Decree of the Government of Georgia, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 78.

²⁰ Law of Georgia on the "Fight Against Corruption", Article 3, Paragraph 3.

²¹ OECD, Managing Conflict of Interest in the Public Service, OECD Guidelines and Country Experiences, 2003, p. 53.

²² Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Kardava, E. ed.), On Approval of the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct

in a Public Institution, Comments on the Decree of the Government of Georgia, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 51.

²³ Ibid., p. 53.

²⁴ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Kardava, E. ed.), On Approval of the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Comments on the Decree of the Government of Georgia, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 60.

²⁵ State Sports Policy Document 2014-2020, 2014, p. 3.

²⁶ Ibid., p. 4.

activity should not depend solely on the integrity of public servants.

4. Principle of Integrity and Ethical Environment Management in Public Service

It is essential to highlight the principle of good faith separately, as it encompasses and implies actions in accordance with relevant moral and ethical values, norms, and rules of behavior. A conscientious public servant acts within their authority and uses their position or power solely to protect public interest based on the law. Integrity in public administration is intertwined with concepts such as ethics and rules of conduct, morality, corruption, conflict of interest, and incompatibility of positions in public service.

Whether a particular civil servant is conscientious is measured by their decisions and actions in preventing unethical behavior, immoral attitudes, corruption offenses, and conflicts of interest. Therefore, adherence to the standard of integrity is crucial in public service.²⁷ Conscientiousness refers to adherence to ethical principles and moral values, even when faced with difficult decisions or the temptation to act otherwise. Acting in accordance with the principle of good faith involves considering the potential impact of one's actions on the institution, the state, or society as a whole. When making decisions, civil servants take into account the rights of others, strive to minimize harm, and promote public interests.

A public institution based on good faith is one that conducts its activities on the foundation of ethical values, where work is performed with high-quality personal and organizational skills. Such an institution not only deserves the trust and respect of the public but also sets a positive example for other institutions. Achieving and maintaining this result requires all public servants to understand the importance of acting in compliance with the principle of good faith and effectively implementing it in practice.

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The issue of integrity is especially important in relation to dismissed civil servants. According to legislation, a dismissed public servant has no right to start working in a public institution within one year from the date of dismissal or to carry out activities in an enterprise they systematically supervised during the last three years. They also have no right to receive income from such a public institution or enterprise.³¹ It is important to highlight the principle of good faith separately, as it encompasses actions aligned with relevant moral and ethical values, norms, and rules of behavior. A conscientious public servant acts within their authority and uses their position solely to protect the public interest based on the law. Integrity in public administration is intertwined with concepts such as ethics and rules of conduct, morality, corruption, conflict of interest, and incompatibility of positions in public service.

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²⁷ Law of Georgia "On Culture", Article 5, Subparagraph "g".

²⁸ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Kardava, E. ed.), On Approval of the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Comments on the Decree of the Government of Georgia, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 40.

²⁹ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Kardava, E. (Eds.), Integrity in the Public Service: Corruption Offences, Conflicts of Interest, and Incompatibility of Office, 2022, p. 9.

³⁰ Gunashvili, D., Makalatia, E., Razmadze, J., Samchkuashvili, T., Siradze, E., Khazalia, Y. (Eds.), Ethics and General Rules of Conduct in Public Service: Practical Manual, Third Edition, Tbilisi, 2017, p. 18.

³¹ Law of Georgia on the "Fight Against Corruption", Article 13, Paragraph 10.

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One severe manifestation of dishonesty is when it leads to corrupt acts. Widespread corruption not only reduces trust in public service but also significantly impacts economic factors. Therefore, any country aspiring to have a functional and effective public service must implement good faith and anti-corruption programs.³³

An important issue in influencing the exercise of official powers of a civil servant is the institution of gifts and the risks arising from them. According to the first paragraph of Article 5 of the Law of Georgia "On Combating Corruption", a gift is defined as property or services given to a public servant or their family member free of charge or on preferential terms, including complete or partial exemption from property obligations, which is an exception to the general rule. This definition includes both direct and indirect influence. Direct influence occurs when the public servant is the recipient of the gift and can use their authority in exchange for the gift to make a decision that is an exception to the general rule. Indirect influence occurs when the recipient of the gift is not the public servant directly but a member of their family, such as a spouse, minor

child, stepchild, or a person permanently residing with them.³⁴

Why is it important to regulate the issue of gifts, and what should a civil servant consider when offered a gift? The purpose of regulating gifts is to create a bona fide and corruption-free environment in public service, ensuring impartial and free decisions by civil servants. Gift policy promotes the introduction of important principles of public administration such as legality, integrity, objectivity, impartiality, equality, independence, transparency, and accountability.³⁵

One of the important roles in the ethical environment management process is played by the head of the institution and their management style. The head of the institution plays a decisive role in forming organizational culture and adherence to ethical principles. A supervisor who prioritizes action in accordance with ethical standards and respects ethical views can establish and develop a culture of ethical behavior throughout the institution. While legislation lays the foundation for ethical governance, the management style of the head of the institution contributes significantly to the realization of ethical principles.

Leaders are limited in certain actions to promote an ethical environment. For example, a civil servant in a leadership position should avoid an autocratic style of governance and instead provide an open and free environment for initiatives and criticism. Additionally, they should assign tasks within the competence of subordinate public servants and ensure the effective distribution of working time and functions among them. Within their authority, they should identify areas where there may be a risk of conflict of interest and develop mechanisms to ensure the reduction and/or effective management of these risks. Leaders should also be objective and impartial, facilitating the adoption of unbiased decisions and avoiding the encouragement of wrongful actions.

Creating a collegial environment and providing access to vocational education for public servants under their supervision is crucial. Leaders should also facilitate the involvement of their subordinates in various professional development programs. By promoting such an environment, the head of the institution not only ensures adherence to ethical standards but also fosters a culture of continuous improvement and integrity within the organization.³⁶

In addition to officials holding leadership positions in the civil service, each civil servant is obliged to determine the measures and tasks to be carried out according to priority and, in case of any difficulty, apply to their direct supervisor. A civil servant must reasonably distribute working time and resources when performing tasks, assess possible risks when planning

³² Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Kardava, E. ed.), On Approval of the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Comments on the Decree of the Government of Georgia, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 49.

³³ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Kardava, E. (Eds.), Integrity in the Public Service: Corruption Offences, Conflicts of Interest, and Incompatibility of Office, 2022, p. 27.

³⁴ Agapishvili, Y., Beselia, G., Tsukhishvili, N. (Kardava, E. ed.), On Approval of the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct

in a Public Institution, Comments on the Decree of the Government of Georgia, Tbilisi, 2018, p. 65.

³⁵ Tsukhishvili, N., Gift Policy in Public Service: Comparative Analysis of International Practice and Georgian Legislation, 2020, p. 6.

³⁶ Government of Georgia, On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Decree of April 20, 2017, No. 200, Article 25.

work, and develop appropriate measures to eliminate them. It is crucial to consider the objectives of the public service when performing work.³⁷

Beyond how a leader should behave, there is a statutory obligation to protect the rights of those under their authority. A civil servant is expected to perform instructions, orders, and other oral or written tasks in good faith. If these tasks are vague, difficult to perform, or if there is a problem of competence, the civil servant is obliged to immediately inform the issuing superior of these circumstances. Additionally, civil servants must not comply with instructions, tasks, and orders that contradict the legislation of Georgia.³⁸

Civil servants are required to act in accordance with the law and are responsible for their actions. The execution of illegal orders from superiors does not absolve them of responsibility for potential offenses. It is important to distinguish the results of executing an illegal task, which in some cases may impact broader state or public interests, and in other cases may not have such a wide scope. However, the primary issue is the illegality of the task, which cannot be measured solely by its impact. The illegality itself necessitates non-compliance regardless of the scale of its effect.

The statutory obligation ensures that civil servants are accountable for their actions, promoting an ethical and lawful work environment. This framework supports the integrity of public service by requiring all civil servants, regardless of rank, to adhere to legal and ethical standards and to take proactive steps to address any issues that arise in the course of their duties.

Conclusion

The exploration of ethics within Georgia's public service underscores its fundamental importance in shaping a transparent, accountable, and effective governance structure. Ethics, deeply rooted in philosophical tradition, continues to evolve, reflecting the dynamic nature of societal values and the complexities of modern governance.

Georgia's journey in establishing ethical standards for civil servants highlights the significance of legislative frameworks in guiding behavior and decision-making processes. From the early provisions in the 1997 Law "On Civil Service" to the comprehensive reforms encapsulated in the 2015 Law "On Public Service" and the 2017 Government Decree, these regulations strive to create an environment where ethical conduct is the norm. The focus on preventing conflicts of interest, managing ethical dilemmas, and upholding principles such as legality, loyalty, and neutrality demonstrates a commitment to fostering integrity within public institutions.

However, the effective implementation of these ethical standards depends not only on legislation but also on the dedication of individuals within the public service. Civil servants are entrusted with the responsibility to act in good faith, prioritizing public interest over personal gain. Their adherence to ethical principles and proactive engagement in ethical practices are crucial for maintaining public trust and enhancing the legitimacy of state institutions.

The continuous refinement of ethical standards and the introduction of measures to address emerging challenges are essential for sustaining an ethical culture in public service. Leaders play a pivotal role in promoting ethical behavior, and their actions set the tone for the entire organization. By fostering an environment of integrity, transparency, and accountability, public institutions can effectively serve the interests of society and contribute to the overall well-being of the nation.

In conclusion, the development of ethics in Georgia's public service is an ongoing process that requires vigilance, commitment, and adaptability. As Georgia navigates the complexities of modern governance, the emphasis on ethical conduct remains a cornerstone for achieving a just and equitable society. The lessons learned and the frameworks established provide a robust foundation for future advancements, ensuring that ethics continues to guide the path toward effective and honorable public service.

³⁷ Government of Georgia, On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Decree of April 20, 2017, No. 200, Article 23.

³⁸ Government of Georgia, On Determining the General Rules of Ethics and Conduct in a Public Institution, Decree of April 20, 2017, No. 200, Article 24.